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Rejected but Redirected: A Teacher's Journey of Faith

2017, a year of hope. An answered prayer from above.

A man who grew up in a small town in the province passed his Licensure Examination for Teachers. While waiting for the result of the board examination, he tried his luck applying in different industries, call centers, factories, even as a bagger in a mall but unfortunately, he was never hired.

Then he prayed. He said: "Lord, what is my purpose? Show me the right direction and the pathway I should take."

Another day passed, and he received a call for a final job interview at one of the fast-food chains in town. While waiting for the interview, the man prayed again: "Lord, what is my purpose? Show me the right way and the correct pathway for my life."

Then a call from an unknown number came. He thought it was the final interview, but it was his older sibling. The phone rang, and his sibling shouted: "You passed the Board Exam!"

At that moment, the story of a passionate teacher began. Truly, the Lord is always listening to our prayers.

Ten years later, that man from an unknown small town became a multi-awarded Science Teacher and was recognized multiple times as Outstanding Teacher of the Year. A declaration of faith and trust in the Lord!